

ISic3622

I.Sicily inscription 3622

Language

Ancient Greek and Latin

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

painted rock face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Melita

Place of origin (modern)

Malta

Provenance

Rabat, catacomb of St. Agata, hypogeum of the rupestral church

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Rabat, in situ

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 645695

EDCS 59500346

EDCS 63800027

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2010.0615

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 59.1083

Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni giudaica e cristiane di Malta. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigrafik*. 168: 202-208. At 204-206 no.3 ph

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